

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT FACTORS OF PRODUCTION DUST ON THE ENVIRONMENT AND THE HUMAN ORGANISM

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ABSTRACT

This article gives an idea of dust as one of the natural phenomena, its structural structure, analyzes the degree of impact of dust on the environment and a living organism associated with production, describes the dangerous and harmful factors that dust can cause. In addition, dust protection measures and methods for quantifying dust are listed.

KEY WORDS AND PHRASES: dust, gas, liquid, natural disaster, production. organism, environment, chronic disease, aerosol, airgel, pneumoconiosis, silicosis, silicosis,

INTRODUCTION.

According to available data, in every 1 m³ of air in large cities there are about 6,000 particles, and when including soot and smoke emitted from vehicles, this number reaches around 30,000 dust particles of various sizes. In fields and gardens, this amount is about 10 times lower, and in mountainous areas it is even less.

Many industrial processes are accompanied by the release of dust and gases of various compositions. Therefore, completely clean air is almost never found, and there is always a certain amount of dust present in the air (from 0.25 mg to 10 mg per 1 m³ of clean air). From this point of view, by studying dust and its composition, it is possible to develop a methodology for studying its impact on living nature.

Dust generated in production affects both the environment and the human

body. By studying this through the disciplines of labor protection, healthcare, and sanitary-epidemiology, it is possible to apply methods to minimize its negative consequences.

In this field, during the Renaissance period, the great and well-known scientist Paracelsus (1493–1541) studied hazardous dust factors arising in mining operations. In his works, he wrote: “All substances are poison and all substances are medicine. Only the dose determines whether a substance becomes a poison or a remedy.” The German scientist Agricola (1494–1555), in his work “On Mining,” as well as the Italian scientist Ramazzini (1633–1714) and the Russian scientist M. V. Lomonosov (1711–1765), paid great attention to labor protection issues in their works. In addition, V. L. Kirpichev (1845–1913), A. A. Bess (1857–1930), D. R. Nikolskiy (1855–1918), V. A. Levitskiy (1867–1936), A. A. Skochinskiy (1874–1960), and S. I. Kaplun (1897–1943) also contributed significantly. The great physician Abu Ali ibn Sino conducted important practical and theoretical work on treating diseases caused by dust exposure, while the great scholar Abu Rayhan Beruni studied the impact of environmental factors on human health. Among national scientists, O. Q. Qudratov in light industry, T. I. Iskanderov in labor hygiene, O. R. Yuldoshev and G. Yormatov in industry and construction, and H. E. G‘oyipov in agriculture carried out deep theoretical and effective practical work in solving issues of labor protection and occupational safety.

In this study, the scientific works and research of the above-mentioned scientists and researchers were used.

Before examining the effects of dust on the environment and the human body, it is necessary to consider its structural composition. Without studying its structure, it is practically impossible to develop a research methodology or to understand the level of its hazardous and harmful effects.

Dust (aerosol) is defined as small particles of solid substances that are crushed or otherwise formed and remain suspended (in motion) in the air for a

certain period of time. This suspension occurs due to the movement of the air itself and the small size of these particles [1].

Dust suspended in the air is called an aerosol, while dust settled on surfaces is referred to as an aerogel. Dust not only continuously affects the human body and leads to occupational diseases, but also causes premature failure of production technologies and equipment, reduces product quality, and worsens sanitary and hygienic conditions in production areas.

According to their formation, dusts are classified as follows:

- Natural dusts – formed independently of human activity. Such dusts include particles generated by wind and strong storms carrying eroded layers of sand and soil, dust produced in plant and animal environments, volcanic eruptions, and dust coming from outer space.

- Artificial dusts – formed as a result of direct or indirect human activity in industrial enterprises and construction. In some branches of industry, for example in the chemical industry, hazardous industrial dusts are released, and their emission can lead to tragic consequences.

Depending on their appearance and composition, dusts are divided into the following groups: organic, inorganic (mineral), and mixed dusts.

According to their structure, dusts may exist in solid, liquid, or gaseous states.

- According to particle size (form), dusts are classified as:

- Visible dusts – particles larger than 10 μm , which can easily settle under their own weight.

- Microscopic dusts – particles ranging from 0.25 to 10.0 μm , which settle slowly to the ground.

- Ultramicroscopic dusts – particles smaller than 0.25 μm , which remain suspended in the air and can only be seen using electron microscopes.

- According to their chemical and physical properties:

- Organic dusts – formed during the processing of materials such as wood, coal, peat, cotton, silk, paper, and other raw materials, as well as dust generated from soil due to plant and animal activity.

- Inorganic dusts – dusts released from various solid substances, minerals, and metals.

Dusts formed from a combination of organic and inorganic particles are called mixed dusts.

MAIN PART.

Dust enters the human body through the respiratory system and through food consumption. Long-term exposure to small amounts of toxic substances (such as lead and mercury dust) can lead to chronic occupational poisoning, while large amounts can cause acute poisoning. Many toxic substances, with an increase in temperature, easily transition from a liquid state to vapor or gas and, in this form, enter the human body through the respiratory organs.

The degree of harmful effects of dust on the human body depends on the amount of inhaled dust, its size, shape, chemical composition, and solubility. As a result, various organs such as the respiratory system, digestive organs, eyes, skin, and others may be affected to different extents. Among the most dangerous consequences are lung silicosis, clouding of the eye lens, formation of a white film on the eye, skin inflammation, itching, and other skin diseases.

Among dust types, dust containing silicon and its compounds is considered the most dangerous. In particular, silicon oxide (quartz), silicate dusts, and dusts of certain metals (such as aluminum) and their mixtures, due to their insolubility, accumulate in the respiratory system and can lead to a disease known as aluminosis.

Soluble dusts, when retained in the respiratory tract, are absorbed into the bloodstream and, depending on their chemical composition, exhibit different effects in the body. For example, sugar dust is harmless, whereas dust from lead, copper, and other metals has toxic effects.

The harmful effects of dust can lead to diseases known as pneumoconioses. These may manifest in forms such as silicosis, silicosis-related conditions, and others.

Silicosis is a disease that usually develops over many years in highly dusty conditions, often during heavy physical labor. This disease is common among workers who have been employed for many years in mining, cement, and alabaster production industries, leading to occupational illness.

The initial symptoms of silicosis include weakness, coughing, and chest pain. At the early stage, these symptoms are mild and noticeable mainly during physical exertion. As the disease progresses, shortness of breath and fatigue occur even during simple activities and even at rest.

Pneumoconiosis may also develop due to exposure to dusts of coal, aluminum, iron, and mixed compositions. Industrial dusts not only cause pneumoconiosis but also lead to other diseases of the respiratory tract, skin, and mucous membranes. These include skin peeling, various rashes, eczema, dermatitis, and similar conditions.

To ensure that dust present in the air of industrial premises and workplaces does not pose a risk to workers' health, it is regulated based on sanitary and hygienic standards known as the "Maximum Permissible Concentration of Dust" (MPC). These include:

- GOST 17.2.3.02 "Hazardous and harmful industrial factors, their classification."
- GOST 12.1.005-88 "Air of the working zone. General sanitary and hygienic requirements."
- SanQvaN 0141-03 "Hygienic classification of working conditions in the production environment according to indicators of harmful and hazardous factors, as well as the severity and intensity of the labor process."

Table 1

Maximum Permissible Concentrations (MPC) of Certain Dusts

No.	Substance Name	MPC, mg/m ³	Hazard Class
1.	Aluminum and its alloys	4	4
2.	Aluminum oxide in disintegration form	2	4
3.	Silicon-containing dusts: a) Crystalline silicon (II) oxide (quartz, cristobalite, tridymite) when content exceeds 70%	1	3
	b) Amorphous silicon (II) oxide in aerosol (fog-like) form when content exceeds 70%	1	3
	d) Crystalline silicon (II) oxide when content is 10–70%	2	4
	e) Crystalline silicon (II) oxide when content is 2–10%	4	4
4.	– when containing more than 10% silicon (II) oxide	2	4
	– when containing 2–10% silicon (II) oxide	4	4
	– when containing less than 2% silicon (II) oxide	6	4
	– when containing more than a certain percentage of asbestos	4	4
5.	Glass and mineral fiber, cement, apatite, soil dusts	6	4
6.	Carbon dust: oil, shale, carbon oxide	6	4

The amount of dust in the air is determined using a testing device called an aspirator. For this purpose, samples of dusty air are taken from the workplace at a height of approximately 1.5 meters from the floor and at distances of 1–3.5 meters or more, then analyzed. Using the gravimetric method, the mass of dust in a unit

volume of air is determined in milligrams. In addition, the dispersion of dust particles is also determined and compared with the MPC.

The volume of air passing through the aspirator rotameter is determined based on the height of the float ring according to the instrument's паспорт (technical documentation). The rheometer device is equipped with four diaphragms that allow adjustment of the volume of air being drawn in. Each rheometer has its own паспорт. That is, it is based on dividing the difference in mass by the volume of air passed through, namely:

$$C_u = \frac{\Delta m_u}{V_0} \cdot 10^3 = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{V_0} \cdot 10^3, \quad (1)$$

mg/m³

In this case:

- amount of dust in the air, mg;
- mass of the filter before the experiment, mg;
- mass of the filter after the experiment, mg;
- volume of air passed through the filter during the experiment under normal conditions, i.e., at an air temperature of 0°C and pressure of 760 mm Hg, expressed in liters.

Measures aimed at reducing the formation of dust in the production environment and its harmful effects on the human body include the following:

- Technological measures – primarily aimed at improving technological processes, comprehensive mechanization and automation of production, as well as sealing production equipment.
- Sanitary and hygienic measures – aimed at reducing dust levels by carrying out disinfection, degassing, and deactivation processes, as well as through local ventilation systems.

- Medical preventive measures – according to Article 9 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Labor Protection,” it is mandatory to conduct preliminary and periodic medical examinations of employees in cooperation with healthcare institutions.

A preliminary medical examination identifies whether existing health conditions in a prospective employee may significantly worsen under occupational hazards. Periodic medical examinations are aimed at preventing the development of acute or chronic diseases related to the employee’s profession.

CONCLUSION. Based on the information presented in the article, the following conclusions can be drawn. Due to the significant hazard posed by dust in the technosphere to the environment and living nature, controlling the amount of dust is of great importance. For this purpose, it is necessary to conduct a hygienic assessment by taking into account the sources of dust in production, the causes of its formation, as well as the composition and quantity of dust present in a given volume of air. Based on the obtained data, appropriate measures should be developed to protect and improve the health of workers.

Such measures are being developed and implemented by our government through legal, organizational, and technical actions. It is not without reason that Article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Labor Protection” defines, as key directions of state policy in the field of labor protection, ensuring the priority of employees’ life and health, the development and implementation of safe equipment, technologies, and protective means, as well as the social protection of workers injured in industrial accidents or suffering from occupational diseases.

In addition, employees engaged in work under unfavorable working conditions are provided, in accordance with established standards, with milk or equivalent food products, therapeutic and preventive nutrition, carbonated salted water, special clothing, special footwear, and other personal protective and hygiene equipment free of charge. The procedures and conditions for providing these are

defined in collective agreements and contracts.

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